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The Constitutional Concept of the Historical Constitution and Illiberalism: The Case of Hungary

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Abstract:

Throughout history, reference to the historical constitution of Hungary, which was the uncodified constitution of the state for a thousand years, was used to achieve different and sometimes conflicting goals. Since 2012, the historical constitution has become a constitutional concept after decades of abandonment. It appears in the Fundamental Law of Hungary (2012) and the jurisprudence of the Hungarian Constitutional Court – both link it to the concept of constitutional identity. This paper claims that the narrative of the Hungarian historical constitution as a constitutional concept that has been becoming predominant in legal texts and scholarly works is conducive to illiberalism. It is so because, instead of leaving it in the domain of historical studies, it has been used by political and constitutional actors to oppose liberal values. Two arguments are presented to justify this claim in the following way. First, the contemporary narratives on the two most important constitutive components of the historical constitution, i.e., continuity and rights expansion, are contrasted with legal measures introduced in the second part of the 19th and the first half of the 20th centuries. This comparison supports the view that the contemporary claims on continuity and rights expansion cannot be verified; on the contrary, they imply exclusion and rights restriction. Second, the relevant jurisprudence of the Hungarian Constitutional Court suggests that the finality of introducing the historical constitution into the constitutional text, and their subsequent linking to the concept of constitutional identity, was to secure the traditional Westphalian understanding of ethnic-national sovereignty, mainly against the rule of law, i.e., EU obligations and globalization.

KEYWORDS: historical constitution, Hungary, illiberalism, right expansion, constitutional identity

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I. Introduction

Starting from the last part of the 19th century but especially after the coming into force of the Fundamental Law (2012, FL),¹ various scholarly definitions have emerged about what the historical constitution of Hungary means, what its importance in the life of the nation is, and how it had been able to change over time. The historical constitution was always a concept used in many different and conflicting ways,² and it has retained this quality in recent years. Hungary did not have a long-lasting written constitution until the adoption of the communist constitution in 1949, which ended the era of the millennium-old uncodified Hungarian historical constitution that governed the eras of the kingdom until 1918³ and monarchy without a monarch (1920-1945). Hungary's post-communist (liberal) Constitution (Act XX of 1949 on the Constitution of the Republic of Hungary, hereinafter: Constitution)⁴ did not contain any reference to the historical constitution, nor did the jurisprudence of the Constitutional Court (CC). The text, however, included specific provisions about the principle of democracy and the rule of law and had a chapter on fundamental rights. These provisions, and the entire substantially amended Constitution (1989-1990), along with the membership to the CoE, NATO, and the EU set Hungary on a special, Western-oriented path instead of the former Eastern one (with the Warsaw Pact, the Council for Mutual Economic Assistance, and socialist ideology on society, state, and law). Since 2012, the historical constitution has become a constitutional concept after decades of justified abandonment. It appeared in the Fundamental Law of Hungary (FL), the illiberal constitution replacing the post-communist one, and the jurisprudence of the CC – both link it to the concept of constitutional identity. The FL requires that the constitution must be interpreted in accordance with the achievements of the historical constitution and that the constitutional identity of Hungary rooted in the historical constitution must be protected.

Against this background, the paper claims that the narrative of the Hungarian historical constitution as a constitutional concept that has been becoming predominant in legal texts and scholarly works is conducive to illiberalism.⁵ It is so because, instead of leaving it in the domain of historical studies, it has been used by political and constitutional actors to oppose liberal values. Two arguments are presented in the following way to justify this claim.

First, the contemporary narratives on the two most important constitutive components of the historical constitution, i.e., continuity and rights expansion, are contrasted with legal measures introduced in the second part of the 19th and the first half of the 20th centuries. The documented history of Hungarian suffrage, minority rights protection under the realm of the Austro-Hungarian Monarchy, and the changes in the form of state after the First World War support the view that contemporary claims on rights expansion and continuity cannot be verified. It is suggested that the situation would be contrary: legal changes of that time rather imply exclusion and rights restriction and support the view of the discontinuity of the historical constitution.

¹ The FL is the new constitution of Hungary, adopted in 2011, by the new constitutional majority of the parliament elected in 2010, without any meaningful involvement of the public or opposition parties.

² A Cieger, "Alkotmányosság és nemzeti identitás – a magyar történelem kontextusában. Vázlat" ["Constitutionalism and national identity – in the context of Hungarian history. Draft"], http://atelier.org.hu/upload/category/mta_elte_atelier/kotoerok1.3_cieger_andras.pdf 56

³ An independent kingdom, later as a part of the Habsburg Monarchy and Austrian Empire, and between 1867 and 1918, part of the Austrian-Hungarian Monarchy (dualism).

⁴ This Constitution, even though, still had the numbering of the original document from 1949, was substantially amended during the democratic transition process in 1989 and 1990, and become a democratic constitution respecting the rule of law and human rights.

⁵ For the purpose of this paper, illiberalism is viewed as a thin ideology challenging different dimensions of liberalism, such as political and cultural. More on this, see Marlene Laruelle, "Illiberalism: A conceptual introduction" *East European Politics* 2022 (38).

Second, the relevant jurisprudence of the Hungarian Constitutional Court suggests that the finality of introducing the historical constitution into the constitutional text, and their subsequent linking to the concept of constitutional identity, was to secure the traditional Westphalian understanding of ethnic-national sovereignty, mainly against the rule of law, i.e., EU obligations and globalization.

In light of the abovementioned, the paper is structured as follows: Section II gives a brief overview of how the term historical constitution has appeared in the constitutional text and the Hungarian literature. Section III will contrast views emerging in the literature about the two components of historical constitution, i.e., rights expansion and continuity, and the legal and social reality of that era when the related reforms were introduced. Section IV analyses the CC's relevant jurisprudence to show how judges got inspired by the scholarly narratives of the historical constitution. Final Section includes concluding remarks.

II. Appearance of the term “historical constitution”

After the adoption of the FL, which is a complete opposite of the post-communist Constitution in terms of *expressis verbis* value statements and historical references,⁶ scholars immediately started to analyze the original version and, later on, its amendments. The term, historical constitution, has been used, again, for different purposes, which is traceable not only in scholarly works but in the case law of the CC, which is due to the vagueness of the term and the fact that the constitutional text uses a concept that implies the lack of a codified constitution. It brings about a sense of anachronism instead of a forward-looking perspective and attempts to justify the Hungarian illiberalism, from both a scholarly and legal perspective.

1. Constitutional text

The preamble to the FL, called National Avowal, as of August 2022, not only gives a narrative of Hungarian history, the Hungarian people, and constitutional development, but it also formulates an aspiration for the future – paradoxically by using the reference to the historical constitution, which belongs to the past. It also provides a narrative of the identity of Hungarians, which is rooted in the historical constitution, and, jointly reading it with other provisions of the FL, it links the individual identity with that of the state. The National Avowal is of utmost importance in the constitutional interpretation, as, since 2012, the FL in its Article R) prescribes that its provisions must be interpreted in accordance with their purposes, the National Avowal, and the achievements of our historic constitution.

In the context of history, the National Avowal portrays victory and half-truth. It mentions the first king, St. Stephen, building the state one thousand years ago; it is proud that “we fought for the survival, freedom and independence of our country” and that “our nation has over the centuries defended Europe in a series of struggles”, and it proclaims that Christianity preserves nationhood. About the 20th century, it expresses that “our nation’s intellectual and spiritual unity was torn apart in the storms of the last century”, not mentioning the roles Hungary played in the World Wars. It also states that Hungary did not have national self-determination between 19 March 1944 (Nazi Germany invaded Hungary, an ally state) and 2 May 1990 (the formation of the first democratically elected parliament after the transition). This narrative originates “our

⁶ See e.g., András László Pap, *Democratic Decay in Hungary* (Routledge 2017), Tímea Drinóczi and Agnieszka Bień-Kacała, *Illiberal Constitutionalism in Poland and Hungary: The Deterioration of Democracy, Misuse of Human Rights and Abuse of the Rule of Law*, Routledge (2022).

current liberty” in the 1956 Revolution, not mentioning the declaration of the Republic in 1989, which not only happened symbolically on the same day when the anti-Soviet revolution of 1956 erupted but was adopted as a result of the Round Table negotiation, and thus with the involvement of the former Hungarian Socialist Workers Party. This party and officeholders of the socialist system became the first constitutionalized „enemy” created by the Orbán regime, which was followed by others: homeless people (2013), non-traditional families (2013), migrants (2018), and LGBTQ people (2019). This process is based on populist rhetoric and emotional politics, resulting in exclusion and the waning of individual liberty, ie, illiberalism.

The narrative of the National Avowal on the Hungarian people contains the following: fighters, defenders, victims, and persons that have outstanding intellectual achievements, talents, and diligence, but the “decades of the twentieth century led to a state of moral decay”, which now ends with the new era of national cooperation established by the FL.

The historical constitution appears in the following formulation (in the originally adopted text of the FL): “we honour the achievements of our historic constitution and we honour the Holy Crown, which embodies the constitutional continuity of Hungary’s statehood and the unity of the nation. It is added that “our historic constitution was suspended due to foreign occupations”, which refers to the Nazi occupation and Communist rule in the 20th century (without making reference to the collaboration with the Third Reich).

Aspiration for the future contains that Hungary will be made great again and that because of the state of moral decay, Hungarians need spiritual and intellectual renewal. Also, “our nation’s intellectual and spiritual unity needs to be preserved”. It implies that, also because of Article R), the FL needs to be interpreted in a way that does not allow division and fragmentation.

The National Avowal gives a narrative of the identity of Hungarians since the Seventh Amendment to the FL (2018). While with this sentence “The protection of the constitutional identity and Christian culture of Hungary shall be an obligation of every organ of the State”, the text of the FL⁷ talks about the constitutional identity of Hungary, the National Avowal declares that of Hungarians: “our identity is rooted in our historic constitution”, “the protection of our identity is a fundamental obligation of the State”. The Ninth Amendment finally linked the individual identity with that of the state: “Hungary shall protect the right of children to a self-identity corresponding to their sex at birth and shall ensure an upbringing for them that is in accordance with the values based on the constitutional identity and Christian culture of our country.”⁸

2. Scholarly works

After 2010, the constitutional provisions involving the terms of historical constitution and its achievements increased the interest in their meaning has increased among scholars and became an intersection type of study field of public law and constitutional history.

Already in 2012, some scholars criticized the National Avowal, claiming that it is too political and does not necessarily genuinely reflect the entirety of Hungarian history,⁹ while others interpreted it as a new narrative of a sovereign Hungarian nation and the extract of Hungarian

⁷ Art R (4) FL

⁸ Art XVI (1) FL

⁹ Nóra Chronowski, Tímea Drinóczi, Miklós Kocsis, ‘What questions of interpretation may be raised by the new Hungarian constitution?’ 1 *ICL Journal* (2012) 41-64.

history.¹⁰ While applauding the content, others asked whether the FL could provide a new value catalogue with which the polity would identify.¹¹ Constitutional law scholars conceptualized these provisions (on the historical constitution and its achievements) as a mere aide to constitutional interpretation, i.e., emphasizing the historical approach,¹² and they expected that the CC would interpret the meaning and conceptual framework of these concepts.

One of the issues with defining these concepts, in both scholarly works and legal procedures, is that the historical constitution is a constitution of many centuries shaped by various laws, declarations, customary law and complemented by extra-legal components, such as the spirit of Hungarians/identity of Hungarians (*néplélek*) and the national genius.¹³ These latter extra-legal categories used by scholars in the early 20th century make it difficult - if not impossible - to define the historical constitution from a legal perspective.¹⁴ This difficulty is overlooked by others who have made considerable effort to prove the *raison d'être* of the term in the contemporary constitutional law as something more than an aide for constitutional interpretation – as scholarly support of the illiberal turn.¹⁵ In this context, the historical constitution is viewed as a concept characterized by its perpetuance, which manifests in legal continuity¹⁶ and has revolved around three components. The first is the maintenance of the feudal division of power, as “nobles waived willingly of the power” and the “former feudal representation was replaced by popular representation”.¹⁷ The second element is the lack of rupture with the past whenever a new beginning came as opposed to what usually happened in Europe, with revolutions and new constitutions. The third component is the extension of rights, as “no rights were withdrawn but extended to those who had not enjoyed them”.¹⁸

The other difficulty is connected to the appearance of the Holy Crown in the text of the FL: it “embodies the constitutional continuity of Hungary’s statehood and the unity of the nation”. Nevertheless, the doctrine of the Holy Crown, closely connected to the era of the historical constitution, held that it embodies the king, the territory of Hungary, and the nobles, as described by Werbőzy, in his *Tripartitum*.¹⁹ In other words, the crown, usually (and in Hungary too, historically speaking), relates to monarchy as a form of state. Nevertheless, the doctrine of

¹⁰ Péter Smuk, 'Nemzetfogalom és történeti narratíva az Alaptörvényben. Doktori Műhelytanulmányok, 2013. 292.

¹¹ Ferenc Horkay-Hörcher, 'A nemzeti hitvallásról', In András Jakab - András Körösenyi, ed, *Alkotmányozás Magyarországon és máshol* (MTA TK Politikatudományi Intézet - Új Mandátum Kiadó, Budapest 2012) 288.

¹² Jakab András, *Az Alaptörvény keletkezése és gyakorlati következményei [Genesis and practical consequences of the Fundamental Law]* (HVG-ORAC, Budapest 2011) 198.

¹³ See Gábor Schweitzer: *A Magyar Királyi Köztársaságtól a Magyar Köztársaságig. Közjog és tudománytörténeti tanulmányok [From the Hungarian Monarchial Republic to the Hungarian Republic. Essays from public law and the history of science]* (Publikon Kiadó, Pécs, 2017) 146, 147. He has used the works of the most distinguished professors, such as Kálmán Molnár (1881-1961) professor of public law and Andor Csizmadia (1910-1985) professor of legal history.

¹⁴ Schweitzer, n. 11, 146, 147

¹⁵ See e.g., István Szabó, *Az ősi alkotmány. Történeti előzmények [The ancient constitution. Historical antecedents]*, In Lóránt Csink, Balázs Schanda, Zs. András Varga, *A magyar közjog alapintézményei [Basic institutions of the Hungarian public law]* (Budapest, Pázmány Press, 2020), Zsolt Zétényi, 'Bevezető tanulmány [Introductory study]', in Zs Zétényi, ed, *A történeti alkotmány. Magyarország ősi alkotmánya [The Historical constitution. The ancient constitution of Hungary]* (Magyarországért Kulturális Egyesület, 2010).

¹⁶ An opposing view can be found in the work of the constitutional law scholar Sente. Eg., Zoltán Sente, 'A historizáló alkotmányozás problémái – a történeti alkotmány és a Szent Korona az új Alaptörvényben [Challenges of historicizing constitution-making - the historical constitution and the Holy Crown in the new Fundamental Law]' 1-3 *Közjogi Szemle* (2011) 1–13.

¹⁷ Szabó, n. 13, 47, 100.

¹⁸ Szabó, n. 13, 109.

¹⁹ It is a collection of Hungarian customary law completed in 1514 by István Werbőczy and published in 1517. More on it in Martyn Rady, *Customary Law in Hungary: Courts, Texts, and the Tripartitum* (Oxford University Press 2015).

the Holy Crown and the idea of the historical constitution has been maintained even under different constitutional and political settings. So, historical changes after the dissolution of the Austrian-Hungarian Monarchy challenged the tenability of the doctrine of the Holy Crown and the idea of the historical constitution in situations in which there was no monarch, but the form of state was officially monarchy (1920-1945),²⁰ and when there was no monarchy (1946-1949),²¹ and in which Hungary adopted codified constitutions, such as the communist one (1949), the liberal (substantially amended 1949 Constitution in 1989 and 1990), and the illiberal one (2011). Some constitutional scholars believe that the doctrine of the Holy Crown is simply incompatible with the European constitutional development after the transition of 1989/1990.²² Others opine that even if this doctrine cannot legitimate any CC decision, it could support arguments.²³

The third challenge of interpreting the history-related FL texts is that the “achievements” of the historical constitution must also be construed. Constitutional lawyers have been skeptical about the rationality of the provision. As the historical constitution contains many components that are nonsense (attached to the feudal state) or unacceptable (restriction of rights), the only rationale for using the term “achievements” (of the historical constitution) could be to filter out these elements. Nevertheless, in this way, only those components will remain to be considered in the constitutional interpretation, which are already compatible with modern constitutionalism and are part of the Hungarian legal system.²⁴ Others, however, claim that the achievements of the historical constitution embody its fundamental values, which transcend the written sources of law and can be found in customary law, and as such, are subject to interpretation. Three principles are identified: the division of power (horizontal and vertical as developed throughout the centuries), the protection of the constitution, and the nation-unification role of the Holy Crown. As for the first two principles, these have been part of the constitutional text and constitutional jurisprudence since the transition – which supports the view of constitutional laws scholars. The actualization of this latter is found in that after Trianon, the national “togetherness” has become even more important, and after the EU accession, it helps preserve the national identity²⁵ - a view that explicitly appears in the jurisprudence of the CC.

III. The contrast

1. Rights expansion

One of the results of the Hungarian revolution and the war of independence of 1848-49 was the reform of voting rights, which also meant the expansion of the “membership” in the Holy Crown (the manifestation of the source of power and subject to national sovereignty). Before 1848, every nobleman was part of the Holy Crown, i.e., part of the national sovereignty, and after 1848, as reminded in the literature on the historical constitution in 2010, all citizens.²⁶ Both the literature and the FL, and its constitutional interpretation,²⁷ mention the protection of minorities, i.e., nationalities, ethnicities (hereinafter nationalities), which is considered the noblest tradition of the Hungarian nation and an example of the rights expansion. This Section

²⁰ Between 1920 and 1945, the governor (head of state) was Miklós Horthy. It is also called the Horthy regime.

²¹ The form of state of Hungary was a republic between 1946 and 1949.

²² See e.g., Szente, n. 14, Chronowski, Drinóczi, Kocsis, n. 7, 2.

²³ Lóránt Csink and Johanna Fröchlich, *Egy alkotmány margójára [On the margin to a constitution]* (Gondolat, Budapest 2012) 131

²⁴ E.g., Jakab, n. 10, 199.

²⁵ Szabó, n. 13, 113-116.

²⁶ Zétényi, n. 13, 55.

²⁷ National Avowal, Arts XXIX and 2 FL, 22/2016 (XII. 5.) decision of the CC [65]

contrasts the narrative on the expansion of rights in the field of the right to vote and protection of nationalities with the then prevailing legal, social, and political circumstances, and highlights that the historical constitution was not necessarily about rights expansion.

In the feudal parliament, noblemen, leaders of churches, and representatives of the “free royal cities” had the right to vote. Act V of 1848 extended the subjects of this political right according to the following criteria: male of 20/24 years old (active/passive right to vote, respectively), ownership of certain property, knowledge of the Hungarian language (for passive right to vote). This reform meant that 7,2 % of the population had the right to vote, which, at that time, was progress. Act XXXIII of 1874 introduced some more restrictions. The first was the ability to pay taxes (those who were behind with the payment could not vote), and the second was that voting must be done verbally (until 1938). It resulted in a situation in which less than 6% of the population had the right to vote, which was 5,3% in 1899. Comparatively, it was very low, as in Europe, at that time, the average was 20-30%. Struggles for suffrage for all started in the 1890’s, and the result was the Act of the People I of 1918 (during the short period of the democratic revolution after the First World War). It established the right to vote for male voters of 21 years old and women of 24 years old who could read and write. The secrecy of voting was planned to be introduced, and it would have meant that 50% of the population had the right to vote, but this rule was never applied. Decree 5985 of 1919 of the new regime changed the law of 1918 and increased the age limit for male voters to 24 years, making, thus, 40% of the population to be entitled to vote. Decree 2200 of 1922 and Act XXVI of 1925 increased the property and knowledge-based criteria and the age limit of women to 30 years. The percentage of the people that had the right to vote decreased to 29%. Act XIX of 1938 further increased the age limit for men (to 26 years), maintained the age limit for women (30 years), and introduced certain property and knowledge-based criteria.²⁸

Hungary’s Act on the Equality of Nationality Rights (hereinafter: Nationalities Act) of 1868 is said to be very advanced²⁹ in the multinational Austro-Hungarian Monarchy at the time when the focus was the sovereign nation-state. The preamble of the Act (1868) guaranteed that all citizens of the Kingdom of Hungary (as part of the Austro-Hungarian Monarchy), regardless of their nationality, constituted politically a single nation, i.e., the indivisible, unitary Hungarian nation under the constitution. It also declared that there should be no differentiation between the members of the united nation save for the official usage of the current languages and insofar as necessitated by practical considerations. The Hungarian governments did not necessarily respect this Act, and while nationalities tried to fight for their independence and rights, Hungarian politics was featured by magyarization, which, as researches show, did not include repression or violent conflicts.³⁰ Nevertheless, despite the law, the use of minority

²⁸ See eg, Simándi Irén, *Küzdelem a nők parlamenti választójogáért Magyarországon 1848–1938 [Fight for women’s suffrage in Hungary 1848–1938]* (Gondolat Kiadó, Budapest, 2009).

²⁹ Noémi Nagy, Linguistic Legislation in Hungary during the Era of Dualism. In Wakounig, Marija – Kühnel, Ferdinand, eds, *Central Europe (Re-)visited – A Multi-Perspective Approach to a Region* (Europa Orientalis, Institut für Osteuropäische Geschichte. LIT Verlag, Berlin – Wien, 2015) 229–245; Dóra Frey, ‘Az Osztrák-Magyar Monarchia és a nemzetiségek – különös tekintettel a Birodalmi Tanácsban képviselt országokra [The Habsburg-Hungarian Monarchy and the nationalities - with special regard to the countries represented in the Imperial Council]’, [chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/viewer.html?pdfurl=http%3A%2F%2Ffacta.bibl.u-szeged.hu%2F70635%2F1%2Fjuridpol_forum_009_001_027-044.pdf&clen=226357&chunk=true](http://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/viewer.html?pdfurl=http%3A%2F%2Ffacta.bibl.u-szeged.hu%2F70635%2F1%2Fjuridpol_forum_009_001_027-044.pdf&clen=226357&chunk=true) 28-44. An overview: Szentgáli-Tóth Boldizsár and Gerő Anna, Az 1868-as nemzetiségi törvény és a politikai nemzet koncepciójának utólagos értékelése [Act 1868 on nationalities and the ex-post evaluation of the concept of political nation], 2 *Erdélyi Jogélet* (2020) 84-105.

³⁰ Frey, n. 25.

languages was banished almost entirely from administration and even justice, Hungarian names for settlements were introduced, and Hungarian language and historical narratives dominated at schools.³¹ This administrative magyarization was slow, uneven across domains, and contingent on local power dynamics³² but existed and was challenged.³³ Over the years, the ethnic antagonisms worsened, and there was no rising social class strong enough that could have changed the system, breaking through the fixed pattern of class, religion, and regions.³⁴

The 1868 Nationalities Act was discussed in the lower house of the Parliament for six days, and the opinion of the majority, i.e., that there is a united Hungarian political nation and no other nationality is considered to be a nation, was adopted out of the three submitted draft laws. In the parliamentary debate,³⁵ both the majority and the minority opinion relied on the argument of the historical constitution to support their own claims. Several arguments supported the concept of a united nation. They referred to the principles of the historical constitution, the lack of fight of nationalities, the claim that it has always been like this, a united country was guarded by the ancestors, the sentiment that Hungarians deserve this type of nationhood. It was also reminded that a united nation was also necessary due to the national administrative law and, that Hungary is a historically created unity that cannot be dissolved. They also argued that the draft law submitted by the minorities intended to dissolve this unity. Indeed, the arguments of the nationalities consisted of their sentiments and the demands of the new era. These demands required a distance from the old terms and laws and a way of thinking based on the spirit of the new age. They also used the argument of the historical constitution when highlighting that laws dating back to Saint Stephan recognized them as “nation”, these nationalities had de facto existed in the Hungarian territory until 1848, there was no political nation, and the county system evidenced that Hungary had not been a country demanding a unified state.³⁶ Nevertheless, the result of the debate was the mentioned Act, signaling that the liberal Hungarian elite at that time insisted on the status quo and adopted the concept of the French-type nation-state. Nonetheless the provided rights and autonomies, the Act was not properly implemented. The unresolved minority issue is viewed as one of the main causes for the collapse of dualist Hungary.³⁷ Just as the history of the right to vote, it did not represent any inclusive attitude but focused on the status quo and an exclusive understanding of sovereignty, which certainly was one of the legitimate options for the decision-makers.

These examples illustrate that the expansion of rights, an important component of the historical constitution in the narratives of some contemporary authors, was, contrary to their narratives, not consistent and free from retrogression at all. There seem to be more arguments against the continuity of the historical constitution in a republican era than supporting it. The following Section discusses the relevant jurisprudence of the CC. The CC also gives its own narrative on the historical constitution in its interpretation of the relevant provisions of the FL. This review

³¹ See eg, László Marác, ‘Multilingualism in the Transleithanian part of the Austro-Hungarian Empire (1867-1918): Policy and practice’ 13.2 *Jezikoslovlje* (2012) 287-288.

³² Ágoston Berecz, ‘Top-down and bottom-up Magyarization in multiethnic Banat towns under dualist Hungary (1867–1914)’ 28:3 *European Review of History: Revue européenne d'histoire* (2021) 422-440.

³³ See, for instance, the Transylvanian Memorandum, which was sent to Emperor-King Franz Joseph in 1892. Leaders of the Romanians of Transylvania asked for equal ethnic rights with the Hungarians and demanded an end to persecutions and Magyarization attempts. The Memorandum met with refusal.

³⁴ Marác, n. 27, 295.

³⁵ Based on the presentation of Noémi Nagy at the conference „Történelem, alkotmány és identitás Magyarországon” [History, constitution and identity in Hungary] on 18 November 2021, Budapest.

³⁶ A nemzetiségi törvény képviselőházi vitája, 1868. november 24–29 [Debate on the Act on Nationalities, 24-29 November 1868]. *Képviselőházi napló*, 1865. XI. kötet. 5-185.

³⁷ Marác, n. 27, 295.

might seem to break the previous logic of presenting continuity and rights expansion because the CC interprets and apply what is in the constitutional text, based on the content and request of the petition it receives. Nevertheless, by discussing the CC's concept of the historical constitution, along with that of the term constitutional identity, this Section could provide important impetus for supporting the argument of this paper, i.e., constitutional narrative based on the historical constitution of Hungary is conducive to an illiberalism, i.e., exclusion and inequality.

2. Continuity

Beyond the text of the FL, some in the literature also claim that both the historical constitution and the Holy Crown constitute legal continuity and represent the thousand years old history in which the FL fits.³⁸ A review of the documented legal change, however, proves otherwise.

The question of continuity emerged in the interwar period, during which Hungary was a monarchy without a monarch governed by the regime of the historical constitution, and impliedly by the doctrine of the Holy Crown. After the publication of Act I of 1946 on the republican form of government, scholars agreed on the existence of continuity and considered Act I of 1946 as a written constitution,³⁹ which established a republic, and that the new institutions of the interwar period, i.e., the provisional legal order (the new parliament and the government instead of the monarch and the former parliament) were placed provisionally and beside the historical constitution.⁴⁰ It was also argued that the Holy Crown did not represent the monarchy but, from the 14th century, the state.⁴¹

Nevertheless, the Holy Crown was not included in the national symbols in 1849 and 1918 and between 1946-1949 - which could be viewed as a rupture with the past and looking into the future based on the new constitutional system without the Holy Crown.⁴² It was obviously not mentioned in the communist constitution adopted in 1949, nor in its major amendment in 1972, the preamble of which, on the other hand, referred to the thousand years old history of Hungary. Beyond using the coat of arms displaying the Holy Crown in 1990 as a heraldic ornament, it was only in 2000 when the Holy Crown was brought back into the realm of law with some kind of public law function. Act I of 2000 defined it as a "relic representing the continuity of the Hungarian statehood and independence", which "lives in the consciousness of the nation and the traditions of Hungarian public law".⁴³

This formulation from the year 2000 seems to decide the debate on the nature of the Holy Crown by emphasizing traditions and continuity and considering it a symbol of the Hungarian

³⁸ Szabó, n. 13.

³⁹ Beér János in 1946 and Csekey István in 1947.

⁴⁰ Molnár Kálmán, 'Alkotmányos jogrendünk és a közjogi provizórium [Our constitutional legal order and the public law provisorium]' (Pécs, Dunántúl Rt. Egyetemi Nyomda, 1926) 9-26, referred to by Gábor Schweitzer, 'Közjogi provizórium, jogfolytonosság, új közjogi irány Az 1919/1920-1944 közötti magyarországi alkotmányjog-tudomány vázlat' [The public law provisorium, legal continuity, new directions of public law. Sketch of the Hungarian constitutional law scholarship between 1919/1920-1944] 1 *Közjogi Szemle* 8-17.

⁴¹ Ferencz Eckhart, *A Szentkorona-eszme története [The history of the doctrine of the Holy Crown]* (Budapest, Magyar Tudományos Akadémia, 1941) referred to by: Iván Halász– Gábor Schweitzer: 'Nemzeti jelképek [National symbols]' in András Jakab –Miklós Könczöl –Attila Menyhárd –Gábor Sulyok, eds, *Internetes Jogtudományi Enciklopédia (Alkotmányjog rovat) [Online encyclopaedia of legal studies (Constitutional law entries)]* <http://ijoten.hu/szocikk/nemzeti-jelkepek> (2020) 9.

⁴² In the spring and summer of 1849 Lajos Kossuth was the governor, and during the Aster Revolution (October 1918), which resulted in the first Hungarian People's Republic (1918-1919), then the Hungarian Soviet Republic (1919).

⁴³ Act I of 2000 on the Memory of the founding of the state by Saint Stephen and the Holy Crown

statehood. It also expressively refers to the consciousness of the nation in which the Holy Crown lives. It did not consider the fact that the Holy Crown had not been used in the Hungarian public law in the past 50 years when declaring that it lives in its traditions.

These two elements (statehood and nation) also appear in the National Avowal of the FL: the Holy Crown represents the continuity of the constitutional Hungarian statehood and national unity. Nevertheless, there is no evidence about whether or not the people embraced the Holy Crown during the era of the unwritten constitution. However, what can be known is that the awareness of the population about the (communist) constitution was not high in the 60s and the 80s. In the 60s, the legal knowledge of the population is uncertain, especially in the field of constitutional law,⁴⁴ while in the 80s, the content of the constitution is not really known.⁴⁵ After the transition, there have been no studies specifically surveying the awareness of the population in the field of the historical constitution or the Holy Crown.⁴⁶ It brings us to the issue of whether or not the Holy Crown represents statehood and independence to the extent that the FL creates a constitutional institution (historical constitution) and a basis in which our identity is rooted. In the efforts of finding some clarity in this regard, it is worth referring to the explanatory memorandum of Act I of 1920. The Act is about restoring constitutionalism and the provisional arrangement of the state sovereignty, and, as it explains in its preamble, it was adopted by the new parliament as the sole legal representative of the national sovereignty (Art 2). The preamble recalls that the exercise of the power of the monarch had ceased to exist on 13 November 1918 and that the parliament elected in 1910 also ceased to function on the very same day. Therefore, the exercise of state sovereignty became impossible within the ordinary framework of the (historical) constitution. As opposed to this observation of the preamble, the Act itself refers to the constitution, based on which the new parliament is entitled to determine the other ways of exercise of the state power (Art 1 and 9). The Act created the position of a popularly elected governor (Art 12), the sole representative of the executive power until the question of the head of state would finally be decided. The governor has the same power as the monarch did with certain restrictions (Art 13).

The explanatory memorandum explains, based on the fact that throughout Hungarian history, there had been many governors starting from the 13th century, that whenever it was necessary, the provisional exercise of power had generally been vested on one person. This practice is followed by this Act. Act LVII of 1921 on the dethronement of IV Charles⁴⁷ and Act XIX of 1937 on the expansion of the governor's power and its election.⁴⁸

⁴⁴ A Cieger, 'Alkotmányosság és hazafiság [Constitutionalism and patriotism]' 7-8 *Magyar Szemle* (Vol XXX).

⁴⁵ A Cieger, *Ibid.*

⁴⁶ Gajduszek explains why the Hungarian awareness studies have become less relevant, what methodological challenges the existing research results face, and also summarizes these results. György Gajduszek, 'Empirikus jogtudat-kutatás Magyarországon 1990 után [Empirical legal awareness research in Hungary after 1990]' 1 *Iustum Aequum Salutare* (Vol XIII) (2017) 55–80. Similarly see István H Szilágyi, 'Jogtudat-kutatások a magyar jogszociológiában a rendszerváltást követően I. [Legal awareness research in the Hungarian legal sociology after the transition]' 4 *Iustum Aequum Salutare* (Vol XVII) (2021) 41–71 There are controversial results as well. In a survey on the awareness of the content of the constitution among young people (18-19 years old), this awareness is quite low (12%, in 1998). In another study, from 1998, on the same subject matter, the awareness is around 70% (there were more questions), and yet, H Szilágyi highlights that the awareness about the rules of the constitution was low. H. Szilágyi, *ibid.* 48, 52-53.

⁴⁷ It maintained the monarchy, postponed the decision on the person of the following monarch, and ordered the ministry to make recommendations in this regard at an appropriate time.

⁴⁸ It reiterated the provisional character of Act I of 1920 and acknowledged that the past experiences since 1920 and the international situation warned that maintaining the position of the governor for an undetermined time might have been necessary.

These rules do not contradict the existence of the doctrine of the Holy Crown, as a symbol of a monarchy, and the historical constitution in the interwar period. The form of state of this time was “monarchy without a monarch”, where the role of the monarch was substituted by a governor, as earlier, when it had been necessary. Nevertheless, it can also be argued that Governor Miklós Horthy substituted the king only until the adoption of the Act on dethronement (1921), and after that, he governed the country in its own right. Notwithstanding the difference in opinions, authors place the end of the historical constitution and the applicability of the doctrine of the Holy Crown in a period where Hungary did not have a written constitution and an explicit republican form of government. Act I of 1946 established a republic, without mentioning the interwar period. Its preamble focuses on the end of the monarchy in 1918 and the popular sovereignty, which belonged to the people that decided on the republican form of state in 1946. All of these seem to support the argument claiming that the doctrine of the Holy Crown is linked to the monarchy as a form of state and, along with the historical constitution, was dismissed by the subsequent power holders, i.e., the subject of popular sovereignty in 1946, at the latest.⁴⁹ It was also rejected by the first written and communist constitution, which advocated for the understanding of law and society from the perspective of the Soviet Union. The Holy Crown as a symbol was resurrected as a part of the coat of arms in 1990, and in 2000 it was given more symbolic importance - even public law relevance. The controversy emerged when it was inserted into the National Avowal of the FL, which, due to Article R) became an applicable constitutional provision. It seems that the Holy Crown is intrinsically interlinked to the era of the unwritten, historical constitution, which represents backward-looking constitutionalism.

3. The jurisprudence of the CC

The CC started applying and interpreting the history-related FL provisions since 2012.⁵⁰ It did so partly and mostly at the beginning of the 2010's, as constitutional law scholars have predicted and partly and in the last couple of years, as suggested by advocates of the legal tenability of the concept of historical constitution. It has also coincided with the amendments to the FL. Accordingly, two phases of the jurisprudence of the CC on the historical constitution can be identified. The first phase features controversies that emerged within the body concerning the conceptualization of the term of the “achievements of the historical constitution” and the interpretation of Article R). The second phase brought about the connection of the constitutional identity and the historical constitution emphasizing it “nation-uniting power”.

The identification of what “achievements” are have been surrounded by debates within the CC, and the application of Article R) as an interpretation rule has been considered underdeveloped by judges in their concurring and dissenting opinions.⁵¹ Nevertheless, during the period of

⁴⁹ I have used “at the latest”, as there are diverging opinions on the end of the period of the historical constitution. From one perspective, it could have ended by Act I of 1920 because it declared the parliament as a subject of sovereignty, which in itself contradicts the doctrine of the Holy Crown, which is postulated as a source of power and the subject of national sovereignty. In this context, the historical constitution and the Holy Crown can only be interpreted within the period of the Hungarian monarchy, particularly during the feudal years. I am grateful to Gábor Schweitzer for drawing my attention to this.

⁵⁰ The term of “achievements the historical constitution”, which “We respect” (National Avowal), and Article R) which requires that the FL be interpreted according to these achievements, and the provision of “identity rooted in the historical constitution”, after they appeared in the text.

⁵¹ These critics and controversies appear in concurring and dissenting opinions. See eg, Imre Juhász, dissenting opinion to 13/2013. (VI. 17.) decision of the CC; Béla Pokol, concurring opinion to 28/2013. (X. 9.) decision of

2012-2020, the CC identified, for instance, the following achievements of the historical constitution:⁵² judicial independence, separation of the judiciary and administration, administrative judiciary and justice, freedom of media, historical antecedents of disciplinary accountability of judges, freedom of religion and autonomy of churches, the lawmaking power of local governments.⁵³ Reviewing the jurisprudence of the CC on the topic, it was concluded in both 2016 and 2020,⁵⁴ that the CC identifies laws that are in harmony with the FL as achievements of the historical constitution, and simply does not refer to Article R) when something would not be in harmony with the FL. In this context, however, Article R), as an interpretation rule, is useless.⁵⁵ The CC does not interpret the FL in the light of/in accordance with the “achievements of the historical constitution”, as it would be required by Article R), but select the (ineffective) rules of the historical constitution in order to establish that its rule is in harmony with the FL.⁵⁶ The vague text of the FL in this respect and the uncertainty of the constitutional terms do not serve legal certainty and the rule of law but provide an opportunity for arbitrary interpretation and abusive informal constitutional amendment.

Besides continuing this practice,⁵⁷ in the second phase, after it introduced the term of constitutional identity into the Hungarian constitutional jurisprudence in its first identity decision in 2016, the CC linked the term “historical constitution” with history, identity, and sovereignty that could be abusively⁵⁸ used against the collective entity to which Hungary belongs, i.e., the EU.

Nevertheless, the CC has not activated the concept of constitutional identity against any EU measures but used it to stall some politically sensitive constitutional reviews.⁵⁹ The concept of the historical constitution, however, has been continuously employed. In 2019, a dissenting opinion of Béla Pokol to CC decision 22/2019. (VII. 05) emphasized the difference between the Western and the Hungarian constitutional developments of the 18th century. It explained that the Western model used the idea of constitutionalism against the status quo. As opposed to this, the emergence of the idea of historical constitutionalism in the 1850s in Hungary was not meant to be in opposition to the status quo but against integration into the Habsburg Empire. National independence and the defense of the country’s own statehood were at the center of the reference to the historical constitution. Therefore, goes the argument of the judge of the CC, the achievements of the historical constitution should not be used as “historical anecdotes

the CC; Imre Juhász, dissenting opinion to 28/2013. (X. 9.) decision of the CC, collected by Imre Vörös, ‘A történeti alkotmány az Alkotmánybíróság gyakorlatában [The historical constitution in the practice of the Constitutional Court]’, 4 *Közjogi Szemle* (2016) 45.

⁵² Until 2016: Vörös, n. 47, 44-46.

⁵³ 33/2012 (VII.7), 2/2016 (II.8), 17/2015 (VI. 5), 34/2017 (XII. 17), 6/2013 (III.1), 29/2015 (X.2) decision of the CC, respectively. Some other issues that could hardly be connected to the historical constitution were also identified as its achievement, such as eg, unfairness of the consumer loan agreements, in 3089/2016. (V. 12.) decision of the CC. Vörös, n. 47, 46.

⁵⁴ Vörös, n. 47, and Gera Anna, Történeti alkotmányunk vívmányai az Alaptörvény speciális alkotmányos rendszerében [Achievements of our historical constitution in the special constitutional system of the Fundamental Law], 6 *MTA Law Working Papers* (2021) <https://jog.tk.hu/mtalwp/torteneti-alkotmanyunk-vivmanyai-az-alaptorveny-specialis-alkotmanyos-rendszereben> 21.

⁵⁵ It has been predicted by e.g., Jakab, n. 10, 199.

⁵⁶ Vörös, n. 47, 55.

⁵⁷ Gera, n. 50, 21.

⁵⁸ Tímea Drinóczi, Pietro Faraguna, “European constitutional identity” as a counterbalance for unconstitutional constitutional identities of the Member states, 4 *European Yearbook of Constitutional Law* (2022) (forthcoming), Julian Scholtes, Abusive constitutional identity, 4 *German Law Journal* (2021)

⁵⁹ Tímea Drinóczi, Illiberal constitutional courts and the danger they pose. 4-5 *Państwo i Prawo* 2022

justifying the interpretation of the constitutional rules based on the contemporary democracy” but in the sense mentioned: against integration into an empire.

This message has not gone unnoticed. It resurfaced in CC decision 32/2021. (XII. 20.), which was initiated on behalf of the Government seeking an explicit ruling on the possibility of (non-)application of certain EU measures. It wanted a similar decision to that of the Polish Constitutional Tribunal challenging the primacy of EU law and its interpretation by the CJEU,⁶⁰ which it welcomed in its governmental decision 1712/2021. (X. 9.). This decision is entitled “on the Hungarian opinion be represented in connection to the ruling of the Constitutional Tribunal of the Polish Republic on the relationship between national law and the EU law”, and established the following. First that the referred decision of the Polish Constitutional Tribunal “was triggered by the bad practice of the European Union institutions, which does not take into account the principle of the delegation of powers, and by the stealthy expansion of powers without amending the basic treaties of the European Union, tries to take away powers from the Member States that the Member States never transferred to the European Union”. Second, that “the primacy of EU law can only exist in those areas where the European Union has competence, the framework of which is laid down in the basic treaties of the European Union”. Thirdly, that EU institutions “are obliged to respect the national identity of the member states, which is an inseparable part of their basic political and constitutional system”, while, also “the law-enforcement bodies of the Member States - especially the constitutional courts and courts - are also entitled to examine the scope and limits of the European Union powers”.

In this case of the CC in 2021, interpretation of the FL was sought because, in the view of the petitioner, the implementation of a judgment of the CJEU,⁶¹ because of the ineffective EU measures, might lead to a foreign national’s illegally staying in Hungary for an indefinite period of time and thus becoming part of the Hungarian population. This would violate Hungary’s sovereignty and identity, which are based on its historical constitution. The CC interpreted the FL as follows: where the joint exercise of competences is incomplete, Hungary, due to the presumption of reserved sovereignty, can legislate until the EU institutions take measures necessary to ensure the effectiveness of the joint exercise of competences.

To achieve this result, the CC, among others, conducted the “fundamental rights review” and the “identity review”. The CC argued that an incomplete joint exercise of competences could result in an infringement of the right of the identity of people living in Hungary. Therefore, the state must protect this right. Reading the decision, it becomes clear that the “self-identity of people” is a newly created constitutional right. It finds its origin in a determinism approach that denies individualism and autonomy and individual and social/cultural change, and yet the CC links it to the right to human dignity. The CC stated that a man is born into a given social environment, which can be defined as the traditional social environment, especially through its ethnic, linguistic, cultural, and religious determinants. These circumstances create natural ties, determined by birth, which shape the identity of community members, and “these circumstances cannot or hardly can be changed by the individual, and form an integral part of the human quality that stems from human dignity” [34].

⁶⁰ Blog symposium on the Polish Constitutional Tribunal decision from October 2021 on the relationship between national and EU law. <http://www.icconnectblog.com/tag/poland/>

⁶¹ Case C-808/18. The CJEU found that Hungary’s legislation on the rules and practices in the transit zones situated at the Serbian-Hungarian border was contrary to EU law; and identified breaches of provisions of the Asylum Procedures Directive (2013/32/EU), the Reception Conditions Directive (2013/33/EU) and the Return Directive (2008/115/EC).

Under the identity review, the CC, while recalling the text of the FL and Hungarian history, noted that Hungary has a European identity (National Avowal) and realized that the terms constitutional identity of Hungary and national (state) sovereignty intertwine. It explained, first, that “constitutional identity manifests itself primarily through a sovereign act, adopting the constitution”. Second, it clarified that “taking into account Hungary’s historical struggles, the aspiration to safeguard the country’s sovereign decision-making powers is itself part of the country’s national identity and, through its recognition by the FL, of its constitutional identity as well.” [96]. It also highlighted that “the main features of State sovereignty recognized in international law are closely linked to Hungary’s constitutional identity due to the historical characteristics of our country”. [99]. Against this background, the CC stated that the inalienable right of Hungary to determine its territorial unity, population, the form of government and state structure (Article E (2)) forms part of its constitutional identity.

The political intentions of the Hungarian Government and the case-law of the CC are deeply interconnected in this case, providing the bases for one another, and thus challenging political liberalism in its sense of constraints and respect for the rule of law. The CC’s 2021 decision did not directly confront the mainstream approach of national constitutional courts and was quite restrained if compared, for instance, to the jurisprudence of the Polish and the Romanian constitutional courts,⁶² which challenged the constitutionality of some EU measures, including CJEU rulings. On the other hand, first, this stance also allowed the Government to declare that the CC accepted its position.⁶³ Second, the CC not only gave a blanket authorization to the Executive but also implemented what the Government already laid down in its abovementioned decision 1712/2021. (X. 9.), only two months before the delivery of the CC’s ruling. This decision of the Government was published on 9 October 2021, while the CC’s judgment was delivered on 20 December 2021.

IV. Conclusion

This paper claimed that the narrative of the Hungarian historical constitution as a constitutional concept is conducive to illiberalism. The paper relied on, first, the contemporary narratives of continuity and rights expansion, which are the two most important constitutive components of the historical constitution. These narratives then have been contrasted with legal measures introduced in the second part of the 19th and the first half of the 20th centuries, and the changes in the form of government until 1949. Second, it considered the jurisprudence of the CC on linking two newly emerged concepts of the Hungarian constitutional law: the historical constitution and constitutional identity.

In connection to the narrative on the expansion of the right, the right to vote, and the right of nationalities, it was found that neither of them represented any inclusive attitude. However, their regulation, and thus, the will of the political decision-maker, focused on maintaining the status quo and expressed an exclusive understanding of sovereignty. It should be noted that this understanding, not including the right to vote issues, certainly was one of the legitimate options open for them at that time.

It could be seen that continuity refers to the permanence of the historical constitution and implicitly its fundamental constituent element, the Holy Crown. The idea of the historical

⁶² https://www.ccr.ro/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/Decizie_390_2021_EN.pdf

⁶³ Noémi, Mrav, “Orbán: az Alkotmánybíróság szerint a magyaroknak joguk van saját hazájukhoz”, *Euronews*. <https://hu.euronews.com/2021/12/20/orban-az-alkotmanybirosag-szerint-a-magyaroknak-joguk-van-sajat-hazajukhoz>

constitution, including the doctrine of the Holy Crown, was disrupted at last with the adoption of the communist constitution, or, already in 1946. The lawmaker of the interwar period considered the governor as a substitute for the king, the form of state was a monarchy without a monarch. Even if statehood has continuously existed, it does not necessarily mean that its historical symbol, as a public law institution (the Holy Crown), needs to exist as well. In fact, it was not present in the public law arena after the end of the second world war for decades. Therefore, no continuity can be claimed in which the FL could fit.

In relation to the jurisprudence of the CC, two main points deserve to be made. The first is that the CC cannot really and meaningfully apply the relevant historical constitution-related provisions of the FL. As researches show, it mostly selects the (ineffective) rules of the historical constitution to establish that its rule is in harmony with the FL, but does not make any genuine interpretation in this regard.

The second is that when it does apply it (more “meaningfully”), due to the text of the FL, it necessarily links the term historical constitution with history, constitutional identity, and sovereignty. This interpretation then could potentially be used against the collective entity to which Hungary belongs, i.e., EU. Finally, it seems now that the overall finality of introducing the historical constitution and its achievements into the FL, and its subsequent linking to the concept of constitutional identity was to use it for securing the traditional Westfalian understanding of ethnic-national sovereignty, mainly against EU obligations. It does not seem to offer, neither in the practice nor in the text of the CC rulings, anything that resembles inclusion, protection of rights, unity in diversity, constitutional dialogue and collaboration, and a liberal approach towards constitutionalism and democracy. Moreover, it seems to be relying on one of the narratives of the concept of the “historical constitution”, which asserts that its main focus has always been the defense of statehood against “empires”.

Thus, the historical constitution has been used by political and constitutional actors to jointly oppose liberal values, and therefore, such a constitutional concept is conducive to illiberalism.

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